

OPERABILITY AND EFFICIENCY OF BARANGAY VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN (VAW) DESK IN HANDLING DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN ILOILO, PHILIPPINES

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Abstract: This descriptive-quantitative study using the total sampling dealt with the demographic characteristics such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location/radius distance of barangay from municipality and their operability and efficiency of 42 Barangay Violence against Women (VAW) Desks in managing domestic abuse cases in the Municipality of Sara, Iloilo, Philippines. Each barangay was required by Republic Act No. 9710, often known as the Magna Carta of Women, to set up a VAW Desk office manage by a designated VAW officer to assist victims and survivors of all types of abuse, including economic, psychological/emotional, sexual, and physical abuse. The study evaluated the operability and efficiency of VAW Desk Officers handling domestic violence in 42 barangays of Sara. Utilizing a quantitative framework, the study gathered information on the VAW Desk Officers' operability, efficiency, and demographic profiles. The results showed that most officers are married, have less than 10 years of service, are female, and are 36 years of age or older. The results showed that the VAW Desk Officers were moderately operational and efficient, indicating average effectiveness in handling domestic violence and other related incidence. Significant differences in operability based on the location of the officers were noted, with those located closer to the municipality (within a 2 km radius) performing more effectively than those located farther away.

Also significant differences in efficiency were observed based on educational attainment, with college-educated officers showing higher efficiency. Chi-square and Spearman correlation tests indicated a significant relationship between operability and efficiency. Changes to operations and regulations are suggested in order to increase the effectiveness of services of Barangay VAW Desks.

INTRODUCTION

The Implementing Rules and Regulations of RA 9710 known as the Magna Carta of Women provides for the establishment of a Violence Against Women VAW desk in every barangay. The Violence Against Women (VAW) Desk is a barangay-level facility which serves as a frontline service provider to victim-survivors who experience physical, sexual, psychological, economic, and other forms of abuse. It is managed by a VAW Desk Officer designated by the Punong Barangay and is usually situated within the premises of the barangay hall.

In the study conducted by the Office of Research and Innovation of the University of the Philippines (2024) on violence against women desks in barangays, the results showed that the policies for establishing VAW desks were properly enforced in the city; however, there is still a lack of equipment and resources in certain barangays. In addition, as there are no clear qualifications needed to be a desk officer, the age and educational background of the officers limit their capacity to perform their responsibilities effectively. There is also no regular orientation of the officers on their roles and responsibilities.

This research aimed to determine the level of operability and efficiency of barangay VAW desk operated by VAW officer in handling domestic violence and related incidents. The locale of the study is the 42 barangays of the Municipality of Sara, Iloilo and the designated barangay VAW Desk officer of every barangay served as respondents in this study.

Further the researcher would like to come up a an answers on the following statement of the problems: (1) What are the demographic profiles of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location? (2) What is the level of operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence? (3) What is the level of efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence? (4) Is there a significant difference in the operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location? (5) Is there a significant difference in the efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location? (6) Is there a significant relationship between the operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence and age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location? (7) Is there

a significant relationship between the efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence and age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location? and (8) Is there a significant relationship between the operability and efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence?

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive quantitative research design is ideal for studies aiming to systematically describe a population's characteristics by collecting quantifiable data (Creswell 2009). In this case, the study sought to assess the Operability and Efficiency of designated Barangay VAW Desk Officer of 42 Barangays in Sara, Iloilo, regarding handling of domestic violence in their respective barangay. The use of a quantitative approach allowed for the gathering of structured, measurable data on VAW Desk Officers' demographic characteristics such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location/radius distance of barangay from municipality and their operability and efficiency in handling domestic violence in their barangay level. By employing a descriptive design, the study observed and measured the existing knowledge and skills of VAW Desk Officers in a real-world setting.

Total sampling technique was used in this study, where all 42 barangay VAW desk officers were taken as respondents. The researcher's made questionnaires were validated by 3 panel of expert from Filamer Christian University, Capiz State University and Barangay Health Worker. This composed of 4 parts. First, the demographic profile of the respondents. Second, the operability of the facilities including the equipment utilized to take care of the victim survivor. The third was the efficiency of the services rendered by VAW desk officer with or without the availability of facilities and equipment to victim survivor. Lastly, about the comments and recommendations from VAW desk officers on how to improve their services as well as to achieve their clientele satisfactions. Ethical consideration was properly observed as protocol in research. After the approval of transmittal letter from local chief executive allowing the researcher to conduct study in their area of jurisdiction. Letter of consent were secured to insure the willingness of the respondents as well as to appraise and observe their rights while conducting the study. The same research instrument was used to collect the data from the respondents of 42 barangay VAW desk officers.

The collected data were tabulated and process to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). Mean, Standard Deviation, Frequency and Percentage, One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), t-test, Chi Square, and Spearman rho test were used to analyze and interpret the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Discussion of Demographic Profile of VAW Desk Officers

The table presents the demographic profile of the Barangay VAW (Violence Against Women) Desk Officers, focusing on age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location. Below is a detailed discussion of each demographic characteristic based on the statistical results.

The age distribution of the VAW Desk Officers shows that a majority of the officers (57.1%) are 36 years old and above, indicating a relatively mature workforce in the role of VAW Desk Officers. In contrast, 42.9% of the officers are 35 years old or younger, suggesting that the position also attracts younger individuals, potentially reflecting an interest in addressing social issues early in their careers or as part of community service.

A significant gender disparity is evident in the sex distribution, with females making up 85.7% of the VAW Desk Officers, while males constitute only 14.3%. This result may reflect the traditionally gendered nature of roles related to women's rights and protection, with women typically being more engaged in direct advocacy or support roles related to gender-based violence. The skew towards female officers may also be indicative of their increased sensitivity and personal commitment to the issue, though it is important to note that the inclusion of male officers could be valuable for fostering more inclusive perspectives.

The civil status of the VAW Desk Officers is largely skewed toward married individuals, who account for 78.6% of the total. This could suggest that those who are married might bring a broader understanding of family dynamics and relationship issues that are essential when addressing violence within households. Single officers comprise 16.7%, which might indicate the involvement of young professionals in the field. Only a very small percentage (2.4%) is either widowed or separated, which suggests that the VAW Desk Officer role tends to be filled by individuals who are likely in stable, established personal circumstances.

A large portion of the officers (85.7%) have 10 years or less of service, implying that many of the VAW Desk Officers may be relatively new to the role, possibly due to increased awareness and demand for such positions in recent years. On the other hand, 14.3% of the officers have more than 10 years of experience, which highlights the presence of more seasoned individuals in the role. This combination of relatively new and more experienced officers could provide a balance of fresh perspectives and institutional knowledge in addressing the issue of violence against women.

In terms of educational background, a majority of the officers (61.9%) have completed college, suggesting a relatively high level of education in this role. This may be important as the position often requires critical thinking, knowledge of the law, and an understanding of social services. About 38.1% of the officers have a high school education, which may indicate that the position is accessible to individuals with varying levels of formal education, although a

college degree appears to be a more common qualification for those in the role.

Regarding the location of the officers, a substantial majority (85.7%) work in barangays located far from the municipality, outside a 2 km radius. This suggests that the VAW Desk Officers are primarily situated in areas that may face greater challenges in terms of accessibility and outreach, potentially increasing the complexity of their work. Only 14.3% of the officers are located near the municipality (within a 2 km radius), which may result in easier access to resources, training, and coordination with municipal agencies.

Table 1. Demographic profiles of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location.

Profile	F	%
<i>Age</i>		
35 yrs old & below	18	42.9
36 yrs old & above	24	57.1
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	6	14.3
Female	36	85.7
<i>Civil Status</i>		
Single	7	16.7
Married	33	78.6
Widow/er	1	2.4
Separated	1	2.4
<i>Length of Service</i>		
10 yrs & below	36	85.7
11 yrs & above	6	14.3
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
High school	16	38.1
College	26	61.9
<i>Location</i>		
Near (within 2km radius from municipality)	6	14.3
Far (outside of 2km radius from municipality)	36	85.7
Total	42	100

Table 2 shows the level of operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in their duty operations, specifically in dealing with domestic violence. The key statistic is the mean score of 2.76, which places the level of operability within the "Moderately Operational" range based on the given scale. This indicates that, on average, the VAW Desk Officers are somewhat effective in their duties but are not yet operating at a highly efficient or optimal level.

Table 2. Level of operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence

Variable	Mean
Operability of VAW Desk Officer	2.76

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Very highly operational</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Highly operational</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Moderately operational</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Less operational</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least operational</i>

Table 3 provides the statistical results regarding the perceived efficiency of the VAW Desk Officers, which shows mean value of (3.16): The mean score of 3.16 falls within the range typically categorized as "Moderately Efficient." This suggests that, on average, the VAW Desk Officers are seen as somewhat effective in their roles. While they may perform their duties in a manner that can address domestic violence cases, there is still room for improvement in terms of maximizing their operational efficiency. The "Moderately Efficient" categorization suggests that while the Desk Officers are fulfilling their responsibilities, there are likely challenges or areas that need strengthening to achieve a higher level of performance. In the same manner the standard deviation of 0.89 indicates moderate variability in responses. A relatively low standard deviation, such as this one, suggests that there is a consistent perception of efficiency among respondents, with most individuals rating the Desk Officers' efficiency fairly close to the mean score. However, this also means there are some who may view the Desk Officers as either more or less efficient, possibly due to varying personal experiences or local contexts. This variation could be influenced by factors such as the available resources, training, or support the Desk Officers receive, as well as the complexity or volume of cases they handle.

Table 3 Level of efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence

Variable	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Efficiency of VAW Desk Officer	3.16	Moderately efficient	0.89

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>Very highly efficient</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Highly efficient</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Moderately efficient</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Less efficient</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Least efficient</i>

Table 4 reveals that there are significant differences in the operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in their duty operations concerning various demographic and professional factors: age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location. The operability of the Desk Officers was

measured by their effectiveness in handling domestic violence cases. An independent t-test used to compare these factors.

As to age, 35 years old & below (N = 18) had a mean operability score of 2.79 with a standard deviation of 0.59; 36 years old & above (N = 24) had a mean operability score of 2.74 with a standard deviation of 0.90. The t-value of 0.193 and a p-value of 0.848 ($p > 0.05$) indicate that there is no significant difference in the operability of VAW Desk Officers based on age. This suggests that whether the Desk Officer is younger or older does not substantially affect their ability to perform their duties in domestic violence cases.

As to sex, male (N = 6) had a mean score of 2.73 with a standard deviation of 0.71. While female (N = 36) had a mean score of 2.77 with a standard deviation of 0.79. The t-value of 0.096 and a p-value of 0.924 ($p > 0.05$) show that there is no significant difference in operability based on sex. This indicates that the gender of the Desk Officer does not significantly influence how effectively they carry out their duties.

In terms of Length of Service, 10 years & below (N = 36) had a mean score of 2.81 with a standard deviation of 0.74 and 11 years & above (N = 6) had a mean score of 2.48 with a standard deviation of 1.02. The t-value of 0.949 and a p-value of 0.348 ($p > 0.05$) suggest that there is no significant difference in operability based on the length of service. The data show that both those with shorter and longer service durations perform similarly in their roles.

As to Educational Attainment, High school (N = 16) had a mean score of 2.51 with a standard deviation of 0.65. College (N = 26) had a mean score of 2.92 with a standard deviation of 0.82. The t-value of 1.715 and a p-value of 0.094 ($p > 0.05$) indicate that the difference in operability between those with high school education and those with a college education is not statistically significant at the 5% level. This suggests that, within this dataset, educational attainment does not have a clear, measurable impact on the Desk Officers' ability to perform their duties.

As to location, near (within 2 km radius from municipality) (N = 6) had a mean score of 3.83 with a standard deviation of 0.41 and far (outside of 2 km radius from municipality) (N = 36) had a mean score of 2.58 with a standard deviation of 0.67. The t-value of 4.397 and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) show a significant difference in operability based on location. Desk Officers located closer to the municipality (within a 2 km radius) have significantly higher operability in dealing with domestic violence cases. This difference could be attributed to factors such as easier access to resources, better coordination with other services, or reduced logistical challenges in performing duties.

Table 4

The significant differences in the operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence in terms of age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, and location

Variable	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>Age</i>						
35 yrs old & below	18	2.79	0.59	0.193 ^{ns}	40	0.848
36 yrs old & above	24	2.74	0.90			
<i>Sex</i>						
Male	6	2.73	0.71	0.096 ^{ns}	40	0.924
Female	36	2.77	0.79			
<i>Lenght of Service</i>						
10 yrs & below	36	2.81	0.74	0.949 ^{ns}	40	0.348
11 yrs & above	6	2.48	1.02			
<i>Educational Attainment</i>						
High school	16	2.51	0.65	1.715 ^{ns}	40	0.094
College	26	2.92	0.82			
<i>Location</i>						
Near (within 2km radius from municipality)	6	3.83	0.41	4.397*	40	0.000
Far (outside of 2km radius from municipality)	36	2.58	0.67			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @5% alpha level

ns $p > 0.05$ not significant @5% alpha level

The research also aimed to investigate whether there is a significant difference in the operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers when considering their civil status. The operability in this context refers to how effectively the Desk Officers handle domestic violence cases. To assess this, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare the operability of VAW Desk Officers across different civil status categories. The statistical results are presented in Table 5.

The p-value of 0.110 ($p > 0.05$) suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the operability of the VAW Desk Officers based on their civil status. This implies that whether a Desk Officer is single, married, separated, or widowed does not significantly impact how effectively they are able to perform their duties in dealing with domestic violence cases.

The F-value of 2.149 indicates the ratio of between-group variance to within-group variance, but since the p-value is not less than 0.05, it confirms that civil status does not have a meaningful influence on the operability of Desk Officers in this case.

Table 5

The significant difference in the operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence in terms of civil status

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.576	3	1.192	2.149 ^{ns}	0.110
Within Groups	21.083	38	0.555		
Total	24.659	41			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @5% alpha level

ns $p > 0.05$ not significant @5% alpha level

This study also aimed to examine whether there are significant differences in the efficiency of Barangay VAW (Violence Against Women) Desk Officers in their operations in dealing with domestic violence, based on variables such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location. Efficiency here refers to how effectively the Desk Officers perform their duties in handling domestic violence cases. Tables 6 and 7 show the data.

As to Age, 35 years old & below (N = 18) had a mean score of 2.98 with a standard deviation of 0.83. 36 years old & above (N = 24) had a mean score of 3.30 with a standard deviation of 0.93. The t-value of 1.147 and the p-value of 0.258 ($p > 0.05$) indicate there is no significant difference in the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers based on age. Age does not appear to influence the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers in dealing with domestic violence cases. Both younger and older officers seem to perform similarly in terms of efficiency.

In terms of Sex, Male (N = 6) had a mean score of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.97. Female (N = 36) had a mean score of 3.19 with a standard deviation of 0.89. The t-value of 0.468 and the p-value of 0.642 ($p > 0.05$) indicate that there is no significant difference in efficiency between male and female VAW Desk Officers. Gender does not seem to affect the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. Male and female officers appear to have similar levels of efficiency in their duties.

As to Length of Service Group, 10 years & below (N = 36) had a mean score of 3.14 with a standard deviation of 0.88. 11 years & above (N = 6) had a mean score of 3.27 with a standard deviation of 1.03. The t-value of 0.314 and the p-value of 0.755 ($p > 0.05$) suggest there is no significant difference in efficiency based on the length of service. The number of years a Desk Officer has served does not appear to influence their efficiency in dealing with domestic violence cases. Both newly appointed and long-serving officers perform similarly in terms of efficiency.

In terms of Educational Attainment, High school (N = 16) had a mean score of 2.71 with a standard deviation of 0.72. College (N = 26) had a mean score of 3.43 with a standard deviation of 0.89. The t-value of 2.741 and the p-value of 0.009 ($p < 0.05$) indicate a significant difference in efficiency based on educational attainment. VAW Desk Officers with higher educational attainment

(college level or above) are significantly more efficient in handling domestic violence cases than those with only a high school education. This suggests that higher levels of education may improve a Desk Officer's ability to perform their duties effectively.

As to Location, Near (within 2 km radius from municipality) (N = 6) had a mean score of 3.85 with a standard deviation of 0.49. Far (outside of 2 km radius from municipality) (N = 36) had a mean score of 3.04 with a standard deviation of 0.90. The t-value of 2.134 and the p-value of 0.039 ($p < 0.05$) indicate a significant difference in efficiency based on location. VAW Desk Officers who are located closer to the municipality (within a 2 km radius) exhibit significantly higher efficiency compared to those stationed farther away. This may be due to better access to resources, easier communication, and quicker response times.

Table 6

Independent t-test Results of the Efficiency of VAW Desk Officer According to Age, Sex, Length of Service, Educational Attainment, and Location

Variable	N	Mean	SD	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>Age</i>						
35 yrs old & below	18	2.98	0.83	1.147 ^{ns}	40	0.258
36 yrs old & above	24	3.30	0.93			
<i>Sex</i>						
Male	6	3.00	0.97	0.468 ^{ns}	40	0.642
Female	36	3.19	0.89			
<i>Length of Service</i>						
10 yrs & below	36	3.14	0.88	0.314 ^{ns}	40	0.755
11 yrs & above	6	3.27	1.03			
<i>Educational Attainment</i>						
High school	16	2.71	0.72	2.741*	40	0.009
College	26	3.43	0.89			
<i>Location</i>						
Near (within 2km radius from municipality)	6	3.85	0.49	2.134*	40	0.039
Far (outside of 2km radius from municipality)	36	3.04	0.90			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @5% alpha level

ns $p > 0.05$ not significant @5% alpha level

The ANOVA result in Table 7 shows the Sum of Squares between groups is 11.687, the Mean Square is 3.896, and the F-value is 7.058 with a p-value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$). There is a significant difference in the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers based on civil status. This suggests that civil status may play a role in how effectively an officer performs their duties in dealing with domestic violence cases.

Table 7
Analysis of Variance of Efficiency of VAW Desk Officer According to Civil Status

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.687	3	3.896	7.058*	0.001
Within Groups	20.974	38	0.552		
Total	32.661	41			

* $p < 0.05$ significant @5% alpha level

ns $p > 0.05$ not significant @5% alpha level

Statistical results on Table 8 using Chi-Square test show the relationship between operability and demographic factors. The study also aimed to examine whether there is a significant relationship between the operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in their duty operations and various demographic factors, including age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location.

In terms of Age, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 3.433 with 4 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.488 ($p > 0.05$). The lack of statistical significance ($p > 0.05$) indicates that there is no significant relationship between age and the operability of VAW Desk Officers. This suggests that the operability of Desk Officers in dealing with domestic violence does not vary significantly based on their age group.

As to Sex, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 3.191 with 4 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.526 ($p > 0.05$). The result shows that there is no significant relationship between sex and the operability of VAW Desk Officers. Male and female officers are equally likely to be effective in their operations in handling domestic violence cases.

In terms of Civil Status, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 20.939 with 12 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.051 ($p > 0.05$). While the p-value is close to 0.05, it is still greater than the threshold, indicating that there is no significant relationship between civil status and operability. Therefore, civil status does not appear to have a notable impact on the ability of VAW Desk Officers to perform their duties effectively.

As to Length of Service, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 8.022 with 4 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.091 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.091 indicates that there is no significant relationship between length of service and operability. Therefore, the number of years a Desk Officer has served does not significantly affect how effectively they carry out their duties in dealing with domestic violence.

In terms of Educational Attainment, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 3.409 with 4 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.492 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.492 suggests that there is no significant relationship between educational attainment and operability. Therefore, a VAW Desk Officer's level of education

does not appear to significantly influence their ability to perform their duties effectively in managing domestic violence cases.

As to Location, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 14.179 with 4 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.007 ($p < 0.05$). The p-value of 0.007 indicates a significant relationship between the location of the VAW Desk Officer and their operability. Officers stationed near the municipality (within 2 km radius) are more likely to have better operability compared to those stationed farther away. This result underscores the importance of location in determining how effectively Desk Officers can perform their duties, likely due to easier access to resources, support services, and faster communication.

Table 8

Significant relationship between the operability of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence and age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location

	X^2	df	<u>Asym Sig</u>
<i>Operability</i>			
<i>Age</i>	3.433 ^{ns}	4	0.488
<i>Sex</i>	3.191 ^{ns}	4	0.526
<i>Civil Status</i>	20.939 ^{ns}	12	0.051
<i>Length of Service</i>	8.022 ^{ns}	4	0.091
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	3.409 ^{ns}	4	0.492
<i>Location</i>	14.179*	4	0.007

* $p < 0.05$ significant @5% alpha level

ns $p > 0.05$ not significant @5% alpha level

The statistical results in Table 9 using Chi-Square tests show the relationship between efficiency and demographic factors. The study sought to explore whether there is a significant relationship between the efficiency of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in their duty operations and various demographic factors such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location.

In terms of Age, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 2.928 with 3 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.403 ($p > 0.05$). Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, there is no significant relationship between age and the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. This suggests that the age of a Desk Officer does not affect how efficiently they perform their duties in dealing with domestic violence.

As to Sex, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 1.498 with 3 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.683 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.683 indicates that there is no significant relationship between sex and the efficiency of VAW Desk

Officers. This implies that male and female officers exhibit similar levels of efficiency in their operations related to domestic violence cases.

In terms of Civil Status, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 16.332 with 9 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.060 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value is very close to 0.05 but still greater than the threshold, suggesting that there is no significant relationship between civil status and the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. Although the result is close to being significant, civil status does not have a clear impact on the efficiency of officers in managing domestic violence cases.

As to Length of Service, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 0.457 with 3 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.928 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.928 shows that there is no significant relationship between length of service and the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. This suggests that the number of years a Desk Officer has served does not significantly affect their efficiency in handling domestic violence cases.

In terms of Educational Attainment, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 7.767 with 3 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.051 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.051 is very close to 0.05, indicating that there is no significant relationship between educational attainment and the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. Although the result is marginal, it suggests that the level of education does not strongly affect how efficiently Desk Officers perform their duties related to domestic violence.

As to Location, the Chi-Square value (X^2) is 5.341 with 3 degrees of freedom (df), and the p-value is 0.148 ($p > 0.05$). The p-value of 0.148 indicates that there is no significant relationship between location and the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. This suggests that the geographic location of an officer (whether they are stationed near or far from the municipality) does not significantly affect their ability to perform efficiently in addressing domestic violence cases.

Table 9

The Significant relationship between the efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence and age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, and location

	X ²	Df	Asym Sig
<i>Efficiency</i>			
<i>Age</i>	2.928 ^{ns}	3	0.403
<i>Sex</i>	1.498 ^{ns}	3	0.683
<i>Civil Status</i>	16.332 ^{ns}	9	0.060
<i>Length of Service</i>	.457 ^{ns}	3	0.928
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	7.767 ^{ns}	3	0.051
<i>Location</i>	5.341 ^{ns}	3	0.148

* p<0.05 significant @5% alpha level

ns p>0.05 not significant @5% alpha level

Table 10 shows the statistical results of the relationship between operability and efficiency of Barangay VAW Desk Officers. The purpose of this analysis is to examine whether there is a significant relationship between the operability and efficiency of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in their duty operations related to dealing with domestic violence. The relationship between these two variables was assessed using the Spearman's rho correlation test.

Spearman's rho of 0.635 indicates a moderate to strong positive correlation between the operability and efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. This means that as the operability of the officers increases (i.e., their ability to carry out their duties effectively), their efficiency in handling domestic violence cases also tends to increase. The p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 significance level, indicates that the relationship between operability and efficiency is statistically significant. This suggests that the positive correlation between the two variables is not due to random chance.

Table 10.

The significant relationship between the operability and efficiency of the Barangay VAW Desk Officer in their duty operations in dealing with domestic violence

Variables	Spearman rho	Sig
Operability and Efficiency of VAW Desk Officer	0.635*	0.000

* p<0.05 significant @5% alpha level

ns p>0.05 not significant @5% alpha level

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, several conclusions were drawn:

1. Profile of the respondents revealed that there were six male as VAW desk officer designate barangay by Barangay Captain who were not aware of the requirements as stated in Barangay VAW Desk Handbook that VAW officer must be a woman, so that victim survivor is not hesitant to tell sensitive experience encountered.

2. The perceived efficiency of VAW Desk Officers is rated as "Moderately Efficient." This means that most respondents share a similar view of the Desk Officers' efficiency, though some variability exists, likely due to differing experiences or local factors such as resources and training.

3. The efficiency of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in handling domestic violence cases is not significantly influenced by age, sex, or length of service. However, there are significant differences in efficiency based on educational attainment and location due to resourcefulness and better access to resources and support.

4. No significant differences were noted in the operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in handling domestic violence cases based on age, sex, length of service, or educational attainment. However, a significant difference was observed based on location, with officers located closer to the municipality (within 2 km) demonstrating higher operability. This suggests that proximity to resources and better logistical support may enhance the effectiveness of Desk Officers in performing their duties.

5. The study reveals that there is no significant relationship between age, sex, civil status, length of service, or educational attainment and the operability of Barangay VAW Desk Officers in handling domestic violence cases. However, a significant relationship was found between location and operability, with officers stationed closer to the municipality (within 2 km) demonstrating better effectiveness.

6. No significant relationships between the efficiency of VAW Desk Officers and factors such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, or location. Despite some results being close to statistical significance, none of these factors were found to meaningfully impact the officers' efficiency in handling domestic violence cases.

7. There is a statistically significant moderate to strong positive correlation between the operability and efficiency of VAW Desk Officers. As their operability (ability to perform duties effectively) increases, so does their efficiency in handling domestic violence cases.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed:

1. Barangay captains may observe the criteria in designating VAW Desk Officer stipulated in Barangay VAW Desk Handbook that the officer must be a

woman as required. When male officers are appointed, they ought to receive training on gender awareness. In order to make victim-survivors feel at ease and free to talk about their experiences, efforts should also be taken to give female appointments priority.

2. The Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) may conduct regular monitoring the compliance of each barangay and offering logistical support to officers stationed farther away from the municipality can help close the performance gap and increase the efficacy of VAW Desk Officers in managing domestic violence cases. It is also advised that efforts be made to improve the operability of VAW Desk Officers in remote areas by guaranteeing better access to resources, training, and support services.

3. Training programs maybe conducted and resource allocation be improved in order to increase the efficiency of the VAW Desk Officers and guarantee uniform performance in all domains. Regular evaluations and comments from police and community people may also be helpful in pinpointing certain areas that require enhancement and resolving any regional issues that may be impeding effectiveness.

4. VAW Desk Officers' access to resources, training, and logistical assistance maybe improved in order to enhance their operability in more isolated locations. To increase officers' efficacy in addressing domestic abuse cases, thought should be given to transferring officers or offering more support, making sure that all regions have access to sufficient operational resources.

5. Greater training and resources be made available to VAW Desk Officers in order to increase their effectiveness, especially for those who are stationed in remote locations or have less education. Enhancing the availability of resources, assistance, and opportunities for professional growth will help close the gap and guarantee that all officers are capable of managing instances involving domestic abuse.

6. VAW Desk Officers' access to resources, training, and support services maybe increased in order to increase their operability in more remote locations. To guarantee more efficient processing of domestic abuse cases everywhere, thought should also be given to enhancing logistical support.

7. VAW Desk Officers' operability maybe increased by offering them specialized training, tools, and assistance in order to increase their productivity. Improving their capacity to carry out their responsibilities will probably result in more effective handling of domestic abuse instances. This beneficial association can be further supported by capacity-building programs and routine performance evaluations.

8. Future researchers may conduct deeper and wider scope of studies related to the operability and efficiency of barangay VAW desk officers in handling domestic violence.

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